

Investigation into IN-SITU Shielding Effectiveness Testing of Transport Aircraft

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Abstract

This paper reviews a research effort to identify, develop, validate, and document an approach for conducting in situ electromagnetic shielding effectiveness testing of commercial aircraft. The goal was to measure transfer functions over as wide a spectrum as possible with the range from 100 MHz to 10 GHz being considered a minimum for success. The method developed decreased the cost of such testing with respect to current test methods and does not require special facilities, unusual test equipment, remote sites, or alteration of the aircraft. In addition, the method is applicable to aircraft in production, maintenance or deployment.

Keywords

Shielding Effectiveness, Transfer Function, Reverberation Chamber, Transport Aircraft

INTRODUCTION

The problem of how to economically obtain shielding effectiveness (SE) data on large items such as transport aircraft has been a problem for some time. Current methods require the aircraft be flown to a remote test site where an Open Area Test Site (OATS) has been established. Such facilities are expensive to maintain and operate and the cost of transporting the aircraft and test team to the remote site is also considerable. In addition, it is time consuming to obtain good quality data using an OATS facility on large items such as a transport aircraft due to the large number of samples that must be taken to ensure a thorough test.

For some time the authors of this paper had been investigating the idea of converting a hangar or other large structure into a reverberation chamber. Testing conducted on two large shielded structures [1,2] indicated that it might be possible to obtain useful data from a structure such as a hangar. Discussions with The Boeing Company led to the decision to conduct a formal investigation into the possibility of developing a test methodology that did not require a specialized test facility. Initially, three possible methods of conducting in situ testing were identified. All allow the aircraft to be within a structure such as a hangar or other "reflective" environment. The methods are 1) reverberation method, 2) decay time method [3], and 3) short pulse exci-

tation method [4]. This paper will review only the reverberation method

The reverberation method requires the aircraft to be within a reflective environment such as a hangar. Since no modification of the hangar was allowed (i.e., no mechanical tuner), the internal pattern was altered and/or monitored by changing the antenna locations, orientations, and polarizations within the hangar while using mechanical tuners to vary the boundary conditions within the aircraft.

This project was conducted in three phases. The three phases were conducted during March, August, and October of 2001 respectively using the same hangar. During Phase 1 the hangar was characterized. In phase 2 the shielding of a known test artifact was measured. In Phase 3 the shielding of several cavities of a transport aircraft were measured.

TEST CONSTRAINTS

All measurements were made using spectrum analyzers as receivers and an RF Synthesizer (+10 dBm output max) as a source. The hangar used was not modified in any way. During the evaluation, personnel were allowed to enter and exit the hangar as required to perform their duties. The only restriction placed on the hangar was that the two large doors of the hangar could not be opened during data collection.

The use of such a low power for transmitting introduced the possibility of local ambient signals interfering with the measurements. To insure that the data collected was not corrupted by the ambient signals, the ambient environment was measured immediately prior to collecting each data point. This was accomplished by turning off the RF Synthesizer, taking a reading from the spectrum analyzer, turning the RF Synthesizer back on and repeating the measurement.

Time to conduct the test was greatly influenced by the amount of equipment available (i.e., the number of spectrum analyzers). During Phase 1 only two spectrum analyzers were used and it took three long days to evaluate the hangar insertion loss. For phases 2 and 3, six spectrum analyzers were used, which reduced test time to about a day to

a day and a half to setup and evaluate the hangar insertion loss. Evaluation of aircraft cavity shielding took about a day per cavity using six spectrum analyzers.

HANGAR CHARACTERIZATION

The evaluation of the reverberation method was conducted in three phases. In the first phase, the insertion loss of a hangar was measured. This was accomplished by moving the transmit antenna to 16 locations within the hangar as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Example of transmit antenna orientations for hangar evaluation. h=horizontal, v=vertical, u=up toward ceiling

At each of these 16 locations, the transmit antenna was configured in three separate orientations/polarizations for a total of 48 measurements. As shown in Figure 1, these orientations were such that they did not directly illuminate the intended test volume of the hangar, which would eventually be occupied by an aircraft. Two receivers located within the intended test volume monitored the fields generated. To obtain a thorough evaluation of the hangar, the two receivers were moved to different locations within the test volume three times. This provided a total of six receive locations. These locations were in areas that would be occupied by the test aircraft. The maximum received power for each frequency evaluated was recorded at each location. The first two sets of measurements were obtained using an empty hangar. The last set of data was obtained with a Boeing 757 in the hangar (an unplanned but fortuitous opportunity). For this configuration, the received locations were: 1) under the center of the aircraft and 2) next to the right engine housing. A plot of the data obtained is shown in Figure 2.

The data show that the maximum value of the received signals at the six receiver locations varied by up to 15 dB. The two runs with the aircraft present were not discernibly different than those without the aircraft in the hangar.

Figure 2. Phase I data - Maximum received power for each of the six receive locations

Taking the average of the six maxima, one from each receive location, yielded the “expected” hangar insertion loss as a function of frequency as shown in Figure 3. The average yields a well-behaved value for the expected value of the hangar insertion loss.

Figure 3. Expected value for the insertion loss (IL) of the hangar. Derived from the mean of the data shown in Figure 2. (i.e., Mean of the Maximums)

Phase 1 measurements indicated that SE data on the order of 50 dB could be obtained at frequencies up to about 10 GHz using only a spectrum analyzer and an RF synthesizer. Using RF amplifiers to provide higher excitation power and more sensitive receive equipment should expand the useful frequency range to 18 GHz or more in a typical hangar.

The hangar insertion loss was also measured at the beginning of Phases 2 and 3. As noted above, the data from Phase 1 were collected both with and without an aircraft in the hangar. Phase 2 insertion loss data were collected

without an aircraft in the hangar while insertion loss data from Phase 3 were collected with an aircraft in the hangar. As shown in Figure 4, the repeatability of the insertion loss of the hangar was excellent and not affected by the presence of an aircraft. This indicates that the hangar provides a repeatable test environment without a requirement for internal hangar configuration control.

Figure 4. Comparison of hangar IL data from Phases I, II, and III

VERIFICATION

The second phase of the project was to verify that accurate SE measurements could be made using the environment generated within the hangar. For this purpose a test fixture of known shielding was used as a reference. The SE reference measurement in this case was reverberation chamber data on the test fixture. The test fixture has also been evaluated in an anechoic chamber [5]. The SE measurements were conducted in the same hangar as the initial investigations of hangar insertion loss.

The test technique used is often referred to as the “nested” reverberation chamber technique [6, 7]. This methodology is depicted in Figure 5. Since no modification of the hangar was allowed, there was no mechanical tuner present in the external cavity, as depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Diagram of a typical “nested” reverberation chamber test set-up

Instead, the transmit antenna was moved to multiple locations within the hangar, as described above. The shielding of a cavity can be measured in two ways using this methodology: 1) transmitting into the exterior chamber and measuring the signal within the test fixture or 2) by transmitting internal to the test fixture and measuring the signal within the exterior chamber. The first method is the easiest, since the shielding can be determined by taking the ratio between the power received by the exterior receive antenna and the power received by the internal receive antenna.

$$SE = 10 * \text{Log} \left(\frac{Rx_{Int}}{Rx_{Ext}} \right) \quad (1)$$

The second approach requires that the insertion loss (IL) of the external cavity be known. This requires that two measurement sequences be executed in order to collect the data required to determine the SE.

$$IL = 10 * \text{Log} \left(\frac{Rx_{Ext}}{Tx_{Ext}} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$SE = 10 * \text{Log} \left(\frac{Rx_{Ext}}{Tx_{Int}} \right) - IL \quad (3)$$

TEST FIXTURE DATA

The test fixture measured 1.0 m x 0.9 m x 0.7 m and consisted of an internal framework cut out of 3/16 inch thick aluminum, which was covered with a 0.025 inch thick aluminum skin. A tuner and antenna are installed within the fixture. Five holes were drilled in each of the six faces for a total of 30 holes.

Testing of the test fixture began by mounting it on a dielectric support at a height approximating the height of an aircraft fuselage as shown in Figure 6.

The fixture was evaluated using the two approaches mentioned above (transmitting inside or outside the test fixture). In both cases the tuner internal to the fixture was active. Figure 7 shows a comparison of the data obtained.

The data show excellent agreement between the two approaches.

Figure 6. Photo of test set-up inside the hangar. Test fixture is mounted on a foam support

Figure 7. Comparison of test fixture SE measured in the hangar. Transmit external vs. Transmit internal

Figure 8 shows a comparison of the data obtained from the hangar (when transmitting external to the fixture) to that obtained using the NIST reverberation chamber. The data show excellent agreement with the data measured by NIST. NOTE: The fixture data available from NIST were collected for another project and, as a result, data were only available for the 2 to 4 GHz range [5].

AIRCRAFT TESTING

Once the methodology had been verified using the test fixture, the third and final phase was to conduct testing of an aircraft.

Aircraft testing was conducted by radiating inside the aircraft and receiving external to the aircraft. As with the test

fixture, a mechanical tuner was installed inside the aircraft cavity under test. Aircraft data that had been previously collected using OATS methods were compared to the results obtained using the hangar.

Figure 8. Comparison of test fixture SE measured using the hangar to that obtained using the NIST reverberation chamber

The data obtained using the hangar were in agreement with mean values of previous data (collected using an OATS) for this type of aircraft. The OATS data had variations exceeding ± 10 dB. This can be attributed to the uncertainties associated with conducting OATS testing on such a large structure.

DEVIATION FROM ACCEPTED RC NORMS

The procedure described in this paper was based on the concept of a reverberation chamber. The data collected did not, in all instances, fit accepted reverberation chamber practice. The hangar did not exhibit loading from the aircraft as would be expected when one places a large object such as an automobile in a standard reverberation chamber facility. However, the peak-to-average ratio of the data did fall within the expected values. Also, the distributions of the data did, for the most part, fit the accepted Chi-squared distribution. The data collected suggest that there were large gradients present within the hangar and that the maximum at a particular receive location was due to transmit locations within the general vicinity of the receive antenna, and not due to transmit locations located far from the receive location. The data collected using the decay time method [3] suggest that the maximum received power at each location was not the result of the summing of the impinging signals as would be expected in a properly operating reverberation chamber but rather were the result of a single dominate signal impinging on the antenna.

SUMMARY

It has been shown that it is possible to conduct SE testing of transport size aircraft without the use of specialized or exotic equipment. Initial verification of the reverberation

method was performed using a test fixture with a known SE.

Testing on an actual airframe was in agreement with mean values of previous data collected for this type of aircraft.

Although the hangar did not, in all cases, behave like a true reverberation chamber, the data clearly show that the methodology provides accurate and repeatable SE data. Further study is needed and the existing knowledge base on reverberation chambers should benefit greatly from the expansion of the methodology into the realm of low Q cavities.

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